

Makalenin Türü / Article Type : Araştırma Makalesi / Research Article
Geliş Tarihi / Date Received : 20.06.2023
Kabul Tarihi / Date Accepted : 15.10.2023
Yayın Tarihi / Date Published : 31.12.2023
Yayın Sezonu / Pup Date Season : Güz / Autumn

Examination of The Status and Continuous Anxiety Levels of Swimmers Aged 11-12

Büşra ŞAHİN* Yahya DOĞAR**

Keywords:

Anxiety,
State anxiety,
Trait anxiety,
Swimmer,
Anxiety level

ABSTRACT

Abstract abstract In the study, it was aimed to examine the state anxiety and trait anxiety levels of swimmers aged 11-12 according to various variables. The research was carried out in the general scanning model. The universe of the research consists of 321 swimmers who participated in the 11-12 age group regional competitions organized by the Turkish Swimming Federation. The sample consists of 217 (113 boys, 104 girls) swimmers participating in these competitions. The State and Trait Anxiety Scale (STAS), developed by Spielberg (1976) and adapted into Turkish by Öner and Le Compte (1983), was used as a scale. SPSS program was used in the analysis of the data. Since it was seen that the data fulfilled the parametric assumptions, t test, One-Way Anova test, Scheffe test and Pearson correlation coefficient were used in the analysis. According to the gender variable, it was determined that the state anxiety levels of male swimmers were higher than that of female swimmers. It was determined that there was no statistical difference in trait and state anxiety levels according to family monthly income and age variables. According to the swimming age variable, the trait anxiety levels of the athletes with a swimming age of 6 years and above were lower than the swimmers with a swimming age of 1 month-1 year and 4-5 years. It was determined that the trait anxiety levels of swimmers whose mothers and fathers graduated from primary education were higher than those who graduated from higher education. After all, It was revealed that the trait anxiety levels of the swimmers included in the study were higher than their state anxiety levels, and there was an inverse relationship between state and trait anxiety levels.

11-12 Yaş Grubu Yüzcülerin Durumluk ve Sürekli Kaygı Düzeylerinin İncelenmesi

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Kaygı,
Durum kaygı,
Sürekli kaygı,
Yüzcü,
Kaygı düzeyi

ÖZ

Araştırmada 11-12 yaşlarındaki yüzcülerin çeşitli değişkenlere göre durumluk kaygı ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerini incelemek amaçlanmıştır. Araştırma genel tarama modelinde gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmanın evrenini, Türkiye Yüzme Federasyonu tarafından düzenlenen 11-12 yaş grubu bölge müsabakalarına katılan toplam 321 yüzcü oluşturmaktadır. Örneklemi ise bu müsabakalara katılan 217 (113 erkek, 104 kız) yüzcü oluşturmaktadır. Ölçek olarak Spielberg (1976) tarafından geliştirilen, Öner ve Le Compte'nin (1983) Türkçeye uyarlanmış oldukları Durumluk ve Sürekli Kaygı Ölçeği (DSKÖ) kullanıldı. Verilerin analizinde SPSS programı kullanılmıştır. Verilerin parametrik varsayımları yerine getirdiği görüldüğünden analizlerde t testi, Tek Yönlü Varyans Analizi testi, Scheffe testi ve Pearson

* TSK, Öğretmen, Milli Savunma Üniversitesi Deniz Astsubay Meslek Yüksek Okulu, Yalova, busrasahinn002@gmail.com, orcid.org/0000-0002-8003-8628.

** Doç. Dr. İnönü Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Fakültesi, Malatya, yahya.dogar@inonu.edu.tr, orcid.org/0000-0002-1068-2266

korelasyon katsayısı kullanılmıştır. Cinsiyet değişkenine göre erkek yüzücülerin durumluk kaygı düzeylerinin kız yüzücülerden fazla olduğu belirlenmiştir. Aile aylık geliri ve yaş değişkenlerine göre ise sürekli ve durumluk kaygı düzeylerinde istatistiksel olarak farklılık olmadığı tespit edilmiştir. Yüzme yaşı değişkenine göre 6 yıl ve üzerinde yüzme yaşına sahip sporcuların sürekli kaygı düzeyleri 1 ay-1 yıl ve 4-5 yıl arasında yüzme yaşına sahip yüzücülerden az olduğu görülmüştür. Anne ve babası ilköğretimden mezun olan yüzücülerin sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin, yükseköğretim mezunu olanlara göre daha yüksek olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Sonuçta, Araştırmaya dâhil olan yüzücülerin sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin, durumluk kaygı düzeylerine göre daha yüksek olduğu ve durumluk ve sürekli kaygı düzeyleri arasında ise zıt yönlü bir ilişki olduğu ortaya konulmuştur.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sport is an activity that affects society and individuals in many ways, shaping their emotions and thoughts. It is a psychosocial activity that naturally involves both the feeling of winning and losing and anxiety. Especially in young athletes, this situation is experienced more intensely and can cause them to experience various psychological problems (Taşgın, 2006). These problems reduce the athlete's performance, disrupt coordination, and make their body uncontrollable. Therefore, anxiety needs to be treated and prevented (Nacar et al., 2011). In particular, anxiety that negatively affects athletes' performance in competitions can also lead to psychological breakdown in athletes (Kardaş, 2018).

Anxiety is evaluated in two different ways: trait anxiety (TA) and state anxiety (SA), according to the time of occurrence. TA is defined as a person experiencing constant anxiety without any specific cause (Spielberger, 1966). TA brings problems such as hopelessness, difficulty in decision making, inability to concentrate, sleep disorders, hypersensitivity, increased blood pressure and heart rate (Öztürk, 2019). On the other hand, SA emerges based on certain developments that cause stress in the individual and can increase over time, but it decreases to a minimum level with the elimination or reduction of this situation (Özbaydar, 1983).

Generally, although anxiety is considered to be a temporary condition, the relationship between its behavioral component and performance has not been clearly established, and anxiety has been described as a negative emotional state in its traditional form (Avramidou et al., 2007). Therefore, both high and low levels of anxiety are seen as a problem (Başaran et al., 2009). It is stated that there are many factors that can contribute to the development of anxiety (Demiriz and Ulutaş, 2003). Moderate levels of anxiety have a positive impact on performance compared to other levels of anxiety (Öztürk and Şahin, 2007). It is understood that children who constantly experience high levels of anxiety related to competitions also experience an increase in state anxiety during competitions (Salar et al., 2012), and as anxiety levels increase, their ability to make correct decisions and demonstrate their sporting abilities becomes more difficult (Dönmez, 2013). Therefore, it has been emphasized that there is an inverse correlation between sports performance and anxiety and depression levels (Karakaya et al., 2006).

Based on this information, the physical and mental development of children is important both in terms of their growth as healthy individuals and their sports performance. To ensure the continuity of children's involvement in sports and contribute to their ability to perform at a high level, it is important to identify the factors that increase or decrease anxiety levels before and during competitions. Furthermore, it is believed that investigating this topic will be beneficial for both coaches and athletes in terms of achieving long-term and high-level performance.

In line with the importance of this topic, the aim of the study is to examine the levels of state anxiety (SA) and trait anxiety (TA) of swimmers in the 11-12 age group according to variables such as age, gender, swimming age, parents' educational status, and family income level.

2. METOT

The general survey model was preferred in the study. The survey model is a type of research conducted to reveal or observe any situation in the entire population or a sample taken from the population (Karasar, 2012).

Research Group

The population of the study consists of 321 swimmers who participated in the regional competitions for the 11-12 age group, which took place in Mersin, Turkey, on October 4-6, 2019, as listed in the activity program of the Turkish Swimming Federation. The sample consists of a total of 217 swimmers, including 113 boys and 104 girls who participated in these competitions. The sample size represents the number of individuals that need to be reached with a 95% probability (Cohen et al., 2007).

Data Collection Tools

To collect the personal information of the swimmers, a demographic information questionnaire consisting of 6 items and the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory were used. The adaptation of the inventory to Turkish was conducted by Öner and Le Comte (1983).

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory: The inventory consists of two parts and a total of 40 items, using a 4-point Likert scale. In the Trait Anxiety section, 7 items were reverse-coded, while in the State Anxiety section, 10 items were reverse-coded. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of the inventory was found to be between 0.94-0.96 for State Anxiety and between 0.83-0.87 for Trait Anxiety, based on different measurements.

Research Publication Ethics

Permission was obtained from the Malatya İnönü University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee, with decision number 2019/40 dated 04/05/2021, for publication.

Data Analysis

The SPSS software was used for the analysis. The kurtosis and skewness coefficients were examined to check whether the data met the parametric assumptions. The kurtosis values for the Trait Anxiety scale ranged from -0.98 to -0.04, and the skewness values ranged from -0.29 to 0.55. For the State Anxiety scale, the kurtosis values for the items ranged from -0.96 to -0.13, and the skewness values ranged from -0.33 to 0.78. These values indicated that the data met the parametric assumptions. Therefore, independent samples t-test was used to determine the differences between the means of the two groups, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for more than two independent groups (Çokluk, Şekercioğlu, and Büyüköztürk, 2010). For pairwise comparisons, the Tukey test was preferred as a post-hoc test. To determine the correlation between State Anxiety and Trait Anxiety, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation coefficient was used (Büyüköztürk, 2010).

3. FINDINGS

Table 1. Demographic Distribution of Participants

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	113	52.1
	Female	104	47.9
	Total	217	100
Age	11 Years	101	46.5
	12 Years	116	53.5
	Total	217	100
Family Income Level (TRY)	2000 TRY-4000 TRY	66	30.4
	4001 TRY -6000 TRY	67	30.9
	6001 TRY -8000 TRY	46	21.2
	8001 TRY and above	38	17.5
	Total	217	100
Swimming Duration (Years)	Up to one year	49	22.6
	2-3 years	81	37.3
	4-5 years	55	25.3
	6 years and above	32	14.8
	Total	217	100
Father Education Level	Primary Education	77	35.5
	Secondary Education	55	25.3
	Higher Education	85	39.2
	Total	217	100
Mother Education Level	Primary Education	100	46.0
	Secondary Education	54	25.0
	Higher Education	63	29.0
	Total	217	100

Out of the swimmers, 113 (52.1%) are male, and 104 (47.9%) are female. 101 individuals (46.5%) are 11 years old, while 116 individuals (53.5%) are 12 years old. In terms of income level, 66 individuals (30.4%) fall in the range of 2000-4000, 67 individuals (30.9%) fall in the range of 4001-6000, 46 individuals (21.2%) fall in the range of 6001-8000, and 38 individuals (17.5%) have an income of 8001 or above. Based on the years of swimming experience, there are 49 individuals (22.6%) with 1 month to 1 year of experience, 81 individuals (37.3%) with 2-3 years of experience, 55 individuals (25.3%) with 4-5 years of experience, and 32 individuals (14.8%) with 6 years or more of experience. Among the swimmers, 77 (35.5%) have fathers who graduated from primary school, 55 (25.3%) have fathers who graduated from secondary school, and 85 (39.2%) have fathers with a higher education degree. Regarding mothers, 100 (46.0%) have a primary school education, 54 (25.0%) have a secondary school education, and 63 (29.0%) have a higher education degree.

Table 2. Anxiety levels by gender

	Gender	N	\bar{x}	Ss	Sd	t points	Sig (p)
State Anxiety	Male	113	3.65	0.33	215	6.65	0.00*
	Female	104	3.05	0.58			
Trait Anxiety	Male	113	4.09	0.38	215	0.43	0.66
	Female	104	3.45	0.37			

Significant differences were found in the levels of state anxiety (SA) and trait anxiety (TA) among swimmers based on gender ($p < 0.05$). When looking at the mean scores, it can be observed that male swimmers ($\bar{x} = 2.38$) have higher levels of state anxiety compared to female swimmers ($\bar{x} = 1.96$). However, no significant differences were found in the levels of trait anxiety and state anxiety based on gender ($p > 0.05$). It can be said that male and female swimmers have similar levels of trait anxiety.

Table 3. Anxiety levels by age

	Age	N	\bar{x}	Ss	Sd	t points	Sig (p)
State Anxiety	11	101	0.19	0.49	215	0.31	0.75
	12	116	0.17	0.52			
Trait Anxiety	11	101	0.31	0.34	215	1.32	0.18
	12	116	0.24	0.40			

No significant differences were observed in the levels of SA and TA among swimmers based on age ($p > 0.05$). It can be said that the levels of state anxiety and trait anxiety are similar among the swimmers in the 11 and 12 age groups who participated in the study.

Table 4. Anxiety levels by family monthly income

	Income (TRY)	N	\bar{x}	Sd	F points	Sig (p)
State Anxiety	2000-4000	66	2.16	213	0.20	0.90
	4001-6000	67	2.21			
	6001-8000	46	2.15			
	8001 and above	38	2.21			
Trait Anxiety	2000-4000	66	2.30	213	1.44	0.23
	4001-6000	67	2.33			
	6001-8000	46	2.20			
	8001 and above	38	2.22			

No significant difference was observed in the levels of SA and TA among swimmers based on family income status ($p > 0.05$). It can be said that swimmers from different income groups have similar levels of state anxiety and trait anxiety.

Table 5. Anxiety levels by swimming age

	Swimming Age	N	\bar{x}	Sd	F points	Sig (p)	Tukey
State Anxiety	1 month-1 year	49	2.27	213	0.92	0.43	
	2-3 years	81	2.14				
	4-5 years	55	2.20				
	6 years and above	32	2.12				
Trait Anxiety	1 month-1 year ^a	49	2.44	213	6.26	0.00*	a>d
	2-3 years ^b	81	2.28				

4-5 years ^c	55	2.21	a>c
6 years and above ^d	32	2.10	

*p<0,05

No significant difference was found in the levels of state anxiety (DK) among swimmers based on swimming experience ($p>0.05$). However, there is a significant difference in trait anxiety (SK) based on swimming experience ($p<0.05$). When comparing the scores pairwise, significant differences were observed between those who have been involved in swimming for 1 month to 1 year and those who have been involved for 6 years and above, with the favor of those who have been involved for 1 month to 1 year. Additionally, significant differences were found between those who have been involved in swimming for 1 month to 1 year and those who have been involved for 4-5 years, again with the favor of those who have been involved for 1 month to 1 year.

Table 6. Anxiety levels by father's education level

	Education Level	N	\bar{x}	Sd	F puanı	Sig (p)	Tukey
State Anxiety	Primary Education	77	2.24	214	0.91	0.40	
	Secondary Education	55	2.19				
	Higher Education	85	2.13				
Trait Anxiety	Primary Education ^a	77	2.36	214	3.60	0.02*	a>c
	Secondary Education ^b	55	2.24				
	Higher Education ^c	85	2.22				

*p<0,05

No significant difference was observed in the levels of SA among swimmers based on father's education ($p>0.05$). However, a significant difference was found in TA based on father's education ($p<0.05$). When comparing the scores pairwise, a significant difference was identified between swimmers whose fathers have completed primary education and those whose fathers have completed higher education, with the favor of swimmers whose fathers have completed primary education.

Table 7. Anxiety levels by mother's education level

	Eğitim Durumu	N	\bar{x}	Sd	F points	Sig (p)	Tukey
State Anxiety	Primary Education	100	2.24	214	1.81	0.16	
	Secondary Education	54	2.08				
	Higher Education	63	2.17				
Trait Anxiety	Primary Education ^a	100	2.32	214	3.67	0.01*	a>c
	Secondary	54	2.31				

Education ^b		
Higher Education ^c	63	2.17

*p<0,05

No significant difference was observed in the levels of SA based on mother's education ($p>0.05$). However, a significant difference was found in TA based on mother's education ($p<0.05$). When comparing the scores pairwise, a significant difference was identified between swimmers whose mothers have completed primary education and those whose mothers have completed higher education, with the favor of swimmers whose mothers have completed primary education.

Table 8. State and trait anxiety correlation analysis

	State Anxiety	Trait Anxiety
State Anxiety	---	-0.25*
Trait Anxiety	-0.25*	---

*p<0.01

A significant negative and low-level correlation ($r=-0.25$, $p<0.01$) was found between the levels of SA and TA in swimmers. This result indicates that when there is an increase in state anxiety levels among the participating swimmers, there is a low-level decrease in trait anxiety levels.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Significant differentiation was found in state anxiety (SA) levels among swimmers based on gender, while no significant differentiation was observed in trait anxiety (TA) levels. It was observed that male swimmers had higher state anxiety levels. There are various factors that contribute to anxiety, and it has been expressed that in our society, sports have developed as activities primarily aimed at men (Yaprak & Amman, 2006). It is also noted that men tend to be more competitive in sports (Koivula, 1999) and strive towards competitive activities that enhance their social status (Mota & Esculcas, 2002). Considering these factors, it can be said that the higher state anxiety levels in males compared to females may be attributed to their competitive nature. In addition to studies that did not find significant differentiation between gender and SA and TA levels (Bingöl et al., 2012; Civan et al., 2010; Türkmen et al., 2013), there are also studies that reported significant differentiation. Dönmez (2013) and Demiriz & Ulutaş (2003) found significant differentiation in state anxiety levels based on gender, favoring female athletes. Similar results were obtained in the study conducted by Başaran (2008).

It was determined that there was no significant difference in anxiety levels among swimmers based on age. Age is a factor that can positively or negatively influence anxiety. Each period and age in children's development has its own unique characteristics, and accordingly, children's anxiety levels can vary based on these characteristics (Alisinanoğlu & Ulutaş, 2000). The reason for the lack of significant difference in anxiety levels based on age in our findings may be attributed to the limitation of the swimmers to the age groups of 11 and 12. Similar studies also show no significant differentiation in anxiety levels based on the age variable (Türkçapar, 2012; Civan et al., 2010). In the study conducted by Başaran (2008), it was found that athletes in the younger age group had higher TA levels compared to those in the older age group. This is believed to be due to athletes gradually getting to know their competitors and gaining competition experience.

There was no significant difference in TA levels among swimmers based on their age of starting swimming, while significant differences were found in SA levels. It was determined that swimmers with a swimming age between 1 month and 1 year had higher SA levels compared to those with a swimming age of 4-5 years and 6 years or more. It is generally stated that emotions are under the control of experience. As experience increases, individuals can better control their emotions (Kuter & Öztürk, 1999). Increased experience will also decrease anxiety levels. Therefore, it is expected that the results would show this pattern. Similar studies have yielded findings that are parallel to this study (Baldwin, 2013; Başaran et al., 2009; Zorba et al., 2016).

There was no difference in anxiety levels among swimmers based on their parents' monthly income variable. This result indicates that the monthly income level of the families does not cause significant differentiation in the anxiety levels of swimmers involved in swimming. A study by Aral and Başar (1998) similarly found no significant difference between socio-economic level and anxiety level. However, in similar studies, it has been observed that the monthly income status can have a positive or negative impact on anxiety levels in athletes (Çeviker et al., 2018; Softa et al., 2015).

There was no significant difference in trait anxiety levels among swimmers based on their parents' educational status, while significant differences were found in SA levels. Swimmers with parents who received primary education had higher SA levels compared to swimmers whose mothers and fathers had higher education. According to this result, it can be assumed that parents with lower educational levels may have higher expectations for their children's success, especially in the specific sport they are engaged in. Similar studies generally support our findings (Gacar & Coşkuner, 2010; Kayapınar, 2006).

In conclusion, it can be said that the state anxiety levels of the participating swimmers were lower than their trait anxiety levels, and there was an inverse relationship between state and trait anxiety.

REFERENCES

- Alisinanoğlu, F. & Ulutaş, İ. (2000). Çocuklarda kaygı ve bunu etkileyen etmenler. *Millî Eğitim Dergisi*, 145, 15-19.
- Aral, N. & Başar, F. (1998). Çocukların kaygı düzeylerinin yaş, cinsiyet, sosyo-ekonomik düzey ve ailenin parçalanma durumuna göre incelenmesi. *Eğitim ve Bilim Dergisi*, 22(110), 1-11.
- Avramidou, E., Avramidis, S. & Pollman, R. (2007). Competitive anxiety lifeguards and swimmers. *International Journal of Water Research*, 1, 108-117.
- Baldwin, C. F. (2013). The ref must be blind! Identifying preand postgame stresses of Australian sports referees and match officials. *Sociology Study*, 3(1), 13-22.
- Başaran, M. H. (2008). *Sporcularda durumluk ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi*. Yüksek lisans tezi. Selçuk Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya.
- Başaran, M. H, Taşgın, Ö., Sanioğlu, A.& Taşkın, A. K. (2009). Sporcularda durumluk ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 21, 533-544.
-

- Bingöl, H., Çoban, B., Bingöl, Ş. & Gündoğdu, C. (2012). Üniversitelerde öğrenim gören taekwondo milli takım sporcularının maç öncesi kaygı düzeylerinin belirlenmesi. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14(1), 121-125.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2010). *Sosyal Bilimler için Veri Analizi El Kitabı*. Pegem A Yayıncılık
- Civan, A., Arı, R., Görücü, A.& Özdemir, M. (2010). Bireysel ve takım sporcularının müsabaka öncesi ve sonrası durumluk ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin karşılaştırılması. *Uluslararası İnsan Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(7), 193-206.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L.& Morrison, K. (2007). *Research Methods in Education*. New York: Routledge Publisher.
- Çeviker, A., İnce, İ. & Bayrak, M. (2018). Milli Takım Düzeyindeki Genç Bayan Güreşçilerin Sosyal Kaygı Durumlarının İncelenmesi. *In innovation and global issues congress III* (p. 9).Antalya: Patara, 343.
- Çokluk, Ö., Şekercioğlu, G. & Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2010). *Sosyal Bilimler için Çok Değişkenli İstatistik: Spss ve Lisrel Uygulamaları*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi, 424.
- Demiriz, S.& Ulutaş, İ. (2003). 9-12 yaş çocuklarının kaygı düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre incelenmesi. *Ege Eğitim Dergisi*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Dönmez, K. H. (2013). Samsun ilinde yapılan üniversitelerarası basketbol müsabakalarına katılan sporcuların durumluk kaygı ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 6(5), 243-248.
- Gacar, A.& Coşkun, Z. (2010). Güreşçilerin sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin bazı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. *Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 5(4), 241-250.
- Karakaya, I., Coşkun, A. & Agaoğlu, B. (2006). Yüzücülerin depresyon, benlik saygısı ve kaygı düzeylerinin değerlendirilmesi. *Anadolu Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 7, 162-166.
- Karasar, N. (2012). *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemi*. Nobel
- Kardaş, T. N. (2018). 13-16 yaş arası altyapı futbolcularının müsabaka dönemindeki durumluk kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Spor ve Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 5(2), 109-117.
- Kayapınar, E. (2006). *Ortaöğretim kurumları öğrenci seçme ve yerleştirme sınavı (OKS)'na hazırlanan ilköğretim 8. sınıf öğrencilerinin kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi*. Yüksek lisans tezi. Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Afyon.
- Koivula, N. (1999). Sport participation: Differences in motivation and actual participation due to gender typing. *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 22, 360-381
- Kuter, M. & Öztürk, F. (1999). *Antrenör ve Sporcu El Kitabı*. Ankara: Bağırğan Yayınevi.
- Mota, J. & Esculcas C. (2002). Leisure-time physical activity behavior: Structured and unstructured choices according to sex, age, and level of physical activity. *International Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, 9(2), 111-121. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327558IJBM0902_03
-

- Nacar, E., İmamoğlu, O., Karahüseyinoğlu, M. F. & Aak, M. (2011). Hentbolcuların srekli kaygı dzeylerinin bazı deęiřkenler aısından arařtırılması. *Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(1), 1-12. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/nwsaspor/issue/20138/213798>
- zbaydar, S. (1983). *İnsan Davranıřının Sınırları ve Spor Psikolojisi*. İstanbul: Altın Kitaplar Yayınevi.
- ztrk, F. & řahin, ř. K. (2007). Spor yapan ve yapmayan 9-13 yař grubu bireylerin sosyal yetkinlik beklentisi puanlarının karřılařtırılması (Bursa rneęi). *İlkđretim Online Dergisi*, 6(3), 469-479.
- ztrk, S. E. (2019). *Dart sporcularının durumluk ve srekli kaygı dzeylerinin performansa etkisinin incelenmesi*. Yksek lisans tezi. Bartın niversitesi, Eęitim Bilimleri Enstits, Bartın.
- ner, N. & Le Compte, A. (1983). *Durumluk ve Srekli Kaygı Envanteri El Kitabı*. İstanbul: Boęazii niversitesi Yayınları.
- Salar, B., Hekim, M. & Tokgz, M. (2012). 15-18 yař grubu takım ve ferdi spor yapan bireylerin duygusal durumlarının karřılařtırılması. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy niversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstits Dergisi*, 6, 123-135.
- Softa, K. H, Karaahmetoęlu, G. U. & abuk, F. (2015). Lise son sınıf đrencilerinin sınav kaygısı ve etkileyen faktrlerin incelenmesi. *Kastamonu niversitesi Kastamonu Eęitim Dergisi*, 23(4), 1481-1494.
- Spielberger, C. D. (1966). *Anxiety and Behavior*. New York: Academic Press.
- Tařęın, . (2006). Beden eęitimi ve spor yksekokulunda okuyan đretmen adaylarının meslek kaygı dzeylerinin bazı deęiřkenler aısından incelenmesi. *Kastamonu Eęitim Dergisi*, 14(2), 679-686. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/kefdergi/issue/49104/626644>
- Trkmen, M., Zekioęlu, A., Yıldız, K. & Gral, M. (2013). Antrenrlerin spora zg bařarı motivasyonlarının karřılařtırılması. *Uluslararası Hakemli Akademik Spor Saęlık ve Tıp Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(3), 51-62.
- Trkapar, . (2012). Greřçilerin farklı deęiřkenler aısından srekli kaygı puanlarının incelenmesi. *Gazi niversitesi Eęitim Fakltesi Dergisi*, 32(1), 129-140. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/gefad/issue/6736/90555>
- Yaprak, P. & Amman, M. T. (2006). Sporda cinsiyeti yapı ve spor yksekokulu đrencilerinin yaklařımları. 9. *Uluslararası Spor Bilimleri Kongresi, Tam Metin Bildiriler Kitabı iinde* (ss. 725-726). Muęla.
- Zorba, E., Gksel, A. G., Pala, A. & Zorba, N. (2016). Futbol hakemlerinin msabaka ncesi srekli kaygı dzeylerinin bazı deęiřkenlere gre incelenmesi (Ege Blgesi rneęi). *Spormetre Beden Eęitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14(2), 175-181. <https://doi.org/10.1501/Sporm.0000000294>
-